

Studies on the Metal Complexes with 3-(*o*-Carboxyphenyl)-1-phenyltriazene N-oxide

A. K. MAJUMDAR and S. C. SAHA

Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta 32.

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Complexes like $CuLX$, $NiLX$, $CoLX$, $H[FeL_2]$ and $NH_4[FeL_2]$, where $LH_2 = 3$ -(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-phenyltriazene N-oxide and $X = H_2O$, NH_3 and py , have been isolated and structures discussed on the basis of magnetic susceptibilities, electronic, and infra-red spectra, conductivity and X-ray powder diffraction pattern studies. The copper(II) complexes are all normal paramagnetic; of the nickel(II) complexes, $NiLH_2O$ is octahedral but $NiLNH_3$ is diamagnetic and planar, whereas $NiLpy$ is octahedral mixed with some planar species; the cobalt(II) complexes are high-spin octahedral contaminated probably with some low-spin cobalt(II) or cobalt(III) species. $NiLH_2O$ and $CoLH_2O$ are isomorphous. The iron(III) complexes are spin-free octahedral and 1:1 electrolytes.

THE so-called hydroxytriazenes have been recently shown from IR spectra to exist predominantly in the tautomeric N-oxide form¹. Such ligands, particularly the simplest one, 1,3-diphenyltriazene N-oxide, has been used both as an analytical reagent² and as a complex former³⁻⁷. We have reported the preparation of a new tridentate ligand, 1-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-3-hydroxy-3-phenyltriazene, now being renamed as 3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-phenyltriazene N-oxide, LH_2 (Fig. 1) and studied its

analytical uses in the determinations of titanium(IV) gravimetrically⁸ and iron(III), titanium(IV) and vanadium(V) spectrophotometrically⁹. The present work describes the isolation and characterisation of the copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt(II) and iron(III) complexes formed of this ligand from the electronic and infra-red spectral studies, magnetic susceptibility and conductivity measurements and from X-ray powder diffraction patterns.

Experimental

Preparations

Ligand :

3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-phenyltriazene N-oxide, $C_{13}H_{11}N_3O_3(LH_2)$: The method of preparation of the ligand has been described earlier⁸.

Complexes :

Aquo [3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-phenyltriazene N-oxide] $M(II)$, $M(C_{13}H_9N_3O_3)H_2O$ ($M = Cu, Ni, Co$): Solutions of metal acetates or chlorides (0.002 mole) in water and the ligand (0.002 mole) in hot ethanol were mixed together with stirring. The granular precipitates formed immediately were filtered, washed with hot ethanol and dried in air.

The complexes are slightly soluble in ethanol, methanol and nitrobenzene, insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene and water.

Ammine [3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-phenyltriazene N-oxide] $M(II)$, $M(C_{13}H_9N_3O_3)NH_3$ ($M = Cu, Ni, Co$): Precipitates of the aqueous complexes formed as above were dissolved in excess of strong ammonia and kept undisturbed when the ammine derivatives appeared as fine needles. These were filtered, washed with ethanol and air dried.

The solubility of these complexes are like those of the aquo complexes.

Pyridine [3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-phenyltriazene N-oxide] $M(II)$, $M(C_{13}H_9N_3O_3)C_5H_5N$ ($M = Cu, Ni, Co$): These complexes were isolated from the pyridine solutions of the corresponding metal chlorides (0.002 mole) and the ligand (0.002 mole). The complexes were collected, washed with alcohol containing a little pyridine and air dried.

$CuLpy$ is slightly soluble in organic solvents but the corresponding $Ni(II)$ and $Co(II)$ derivatives are more soluble.

Iron (III) complex, $H[Fe(C_{13}H_9N_3O_3)_2]$: A solution of 0.5 g of iron(III) chloride hexahydrate (0.002 mole) in 20 ml of ethanol was mixed with 1.0 g of the ligand (0.004 mole) in 30 ml of hot ethanol and kept overnight. Shining violet crystals formed were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in air.

The complex is insoluble in water, slightly soluble in methanol, ethanol, chloroform and acetone giving pink colouration but in presence of a few drops of ammonia or pyridine the solubility increases considerably forming deep violet solutions in all those above mentioned solvents.

Ammonium salt of the iron(III) complex, NH₄[Fe(C₁₃H₉N₃O₃)₂]: The iron(III) complex obtained as above was suspended in ethanol and dissolved by adding concentrated ammonia solution, filtered and the filtrate kept overnight. The deep violet crystals formed were washed with ice-cold alcohol and dried in air.

The complex is highly soluble in water, methanol, ethanol, pyridine and slightly so in chloroform.

Measurements of magnetic susceptibility

These were made in a Gouy balance at room temperature with mercury tetrathiocyanato cobaltate as standard.

Electronic spectra

The electronic spectra of the complexes in solution were measured in a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer.

Infra-red spectra

The infra-red spectra of the complexes in KBr pellets or nujol mull were recorded in Perkin-Elmer IR 237 B spectrophotometer.

Conductivity

The conductance of the complexes ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$), in dimethylformamide and methanol was taken in a Mullard conductivity bridge, type E-7566/2. This was directly measured from the scale and this when multiplied by the cell constant, 1.4, gave the equivalent conductance, in mhos-cm².

X-ray analysis

The patterns were taken in a Guinier Camera provided with Cu-K_α-radiation.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analytical data of the complexes studied are given in Table I. The copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes, MLX, with M = Cu, Ni and Co, LH₂ = a ligand molecule and X = H₂O, NH₃ and C₅H₅N(py), are apparently quadricovalent, the triazene acting as a tridentate chelating agent.

Unlike the copper(II) complexes of substituted 1,3-diphenyltriazenes¹⁰ or 1-phenyl-3- α -pyridyltriazene¹¹ studied by us, the three copper(II) complexes with the present triazene, are fully paramagnetic, the magnetic moment corresponding to one unpaired electron. The complexes show one or two broad absorption *d-d* bands above 600 nm in nitrobenzene.

Magnetic properties of the nickel(II) complexes (in solid state) show them to assume different stereochemical configurations depending on the type of monoligand present. Thus, NiLH₂O, with magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) of 3.09 B.M., appears to be octahedral, but NiLNH₃, is fully diamagnetic, probably with a planar structure whereas NiLpy has a magnetic moment of 2.39 B.M., lower than the octahedral value.

NiLH₂O and NiLNH₃ are not soluble in any solvent except methanol in which the former shows crystal field bands at 605, 740 and 860 nm with molar absorbances (ϵ_{max}) of 41.5, 9.4 and 13.1 respectively characterising octahedral symmetry. Another strongly intense peak at 405 nm ($\epsilon_{max} = 25,800$) is a charge transfer band which seems to have completely masked the high energy octahedral band. The diamagnetic NiLNH₃ also shows similar electronic transitions at 410, 560, 735 and 860 nm (ϵ_{max} : 20,400, 60.9, 6.9 and 8.4 respectively) in methanol in which the complex must have turned octahedral. But the

TABLE I—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS

Complex	Nature and decomp. Temp.	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	% Metal		% Nitrogen	
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
Cu(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)H ₂ O	Green powder, 307°	1.95	19.09	18.88	12.37	12.48
Cu(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)NH ₃	Green needles, 300°	1.79	18.99	18.93	16.74	16.69
Cu(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)py	Green needles, 306°	1.79	15.87	15.98	14.22	14.09
Ni(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)H ₂ O	Bright green granular, 200°	3.09	17.52	17.69	12.49	12.66
Ni(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)NH ₃	Brown needles, 285°	Diamagnetic	17.52	17.74	16.80	16.93
Ni(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)py	Green crystals, 160°	2.47	14.78	14.94	14.15	14.26
Co(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)H ₂ O	Brown powder, 250°	4.34	17.74	17.76	12.51	12.65
Co(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)NH ₃	Brown needles, 200°	4.13	17.59	17.81	16.80	16.92
Co(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)py	Chocolate crystals, 200°	4.22	14.93	15.01	14.24	14.25
H[Fe(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃) ₂]	Violet crystals, 220°	5.90	9.94	9.85	14.72	14.82
NH ₄ [Fe(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃) ₂]	Violet crystals	6.02	9.49	9.56	16.74	16.78

spectra of NiLpy in non-polar solvent such as benzene clearly indicates its octahedral transitions at 585, 780 and 900 nm (ϵ_{max} : 94.2, 7.4 and 9.7 respectively), the strongly intense peak at 412 nm (ϵ_{max} , 22,600), being that of charge transfer band. The high molar extinction value at 585 nm suggests the presence of some planar species which may be responsible for the low magnetic value and the octahedral form may be regarded as in conformational equilibrium with the planar species. Intramolecular (planar, diamagnetic, $S = 0 \rightleftharpoons$ Octahedral, $\mu_{eff} = 2.0$ B.M., $S = 1$) equilibrium has also been observed in some nickel(II) complexes of other type of triazene N-oxide¹².

to this structure. But the pattern of CuLH₂O is different from those of NiLH₂O and CoLH₂O showing a different configuration of the complex. The insolubility of copper(II) complex, like those of nickel(II) and cobalt(II) in different organic solvents, suggests a polymeric structure. The electronic spectra of the complex in nitrobenzene also indicates a tetragonally distorted structure and probably due to this X-ray powder pattern differed from the corresponding nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes.

The powder patterns of CuLNH₃, NiLNH₃ and CoLNH₃ are all different. The patterns of the pyridine derivatives, CuLpy, NiLpy and CoLpy are

TABLE 2—ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF THE METAL-COMPLEXES

Complex	Solvent Conc. (M)	Absorption maximum		Molar absorbance
		nm	cm ⁻¹	
Cu(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)H ₂ O	Nitrobenzene (2 × 10 ⁻³)	620	16,130	213
Cu(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)NH ₃	Nitrobenzene (2 × 10 ⁻³)	625	16,000	109
		650	15,380	91
Cu(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)py	Nitrobenzene (2 × 10 ⁻³)	650	15,380	177.5
		Pyridine (6.84 × 10 ⁻³)	640	15,620
Ni(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)H ₂ O	Methanol (1 × 10 ⁻³) 4 × 10 ⁻³	408	24,690	25,800
		605	16,500	41.5
		740	13,510	9.4
		860	11,630	13.1
Ni(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)NH ₃	Methanol (1 × 10 ⁻³) 4.4 × 10 ⁻³	410	24,390	20,400
		560	17,850	60.9
		735	13,600	6.9
		860	11,630	8.4
Ni(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)py	Benzene (1 × 10 ⁻³) 4 × 10 ⁻³	412	24,270	22,600
		585	17,090	94.2
		780	12,320	7.4
		900	11,110	9.7
Co(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)H ₂ O	Methanol 4 × 10 ⁻³	970	10,300	5.0
Co(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)NH ₃	Methanol 4 × 10 ⁻³	950	10,530	4.0
Co(C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃)py	Benzene 4 × 10 ⁻³	960	10,420	11.0

The magnetic moments of CoLH₂O, CoLNH₃ and CoLpy are 4.34, 4.64 and 4.22 respectively. The magnetic moments of these cobalt(II) complexes are lower than usually observed for spin-free octahedral complexes which may be due to presence of some low-spin species or contamination of some cobalt(III) complexes. The complexes are too insoluble in non-coordinating solvents like benzene and carbontetrachloride for measurement of their electronic spectra. In methanol, they show only one low intensity ($\epsilon_{max} = 4\sim 5$) band lying within 950–970 nm suggesting octahedral configuration of the complexes in the solvent used. The other high energy bands have been obscured by the intense charge transfer bands.

X-ray powder diffraction pattern of NiLH₂O and CoLH₂O is identical and so both of them can be assigned the same octahedral configuration since magnetic moments are found already to conform

also different from one another. The structures of the MLNH₃ and MLpy [M = Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II)] are difficult to predict since these seem to have polymeric structure and each complex may differ in the mode of polymerisation.

The violet crystalline iron(III) complex HFeL₂ ($\mu_{eff} = 5.9$ B.M.) was obtained in an attempt to prepare an iron(II) complex starting from an aqueous solution of ferrous sulphate with the same ligand in alcohol. The same violet complex was also obtained on mixing ferric chloride solution and the ligand, both in alcohol, showing the same magnetic moment, 5.8 B.M. However, magnetic moment is not a good criterion of distinguishing between spin-free octahedral iron(II) and iron(III) complexes (the magnetic moment values 5.7–5.8 B.M. lying in the border line). Conductivities of the complexes have been measured in dimethyl formamide, the results (48 and 51 ohm⁻¹cm⁻¹) showing both to be 1:1

electrolyte. Also the ammonium salts prepared from the acid complexes in methanol have the same electrolytic behaviour (80 and 85 $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$) which discard formation of any iron(II) complex of the composition H_2FeL_2 or its ammonium salt, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{FeL}_2$. The I.R. spectra of the two acid complexes are identical. It may, therefore, be concluded that, the same iron(III) complex has been formed in both the cases, the iron(II) ion being oxidised to iron(III) state during the course of complex formation.

The Infra-red spectra

In the infra-red spectrum of the ligand its N-oxide structure is shown from the appearance of a sharp N-H stretch at 3235 cm^{-1} . The O-H and the asymmetric stretches of the carboxyl group appear around 2970 cm^{-1} (broad) and at 1680 cm^{-1} respectively in KBr pellets.

The N-H stretch of the ligand disappears in all the complexes and the asymmetric stretch of the carboxyl group is so much lowered that its correct assignment is not possible since other bands appear along with it.

In the aquo complexes, the presence of water is confirmed from the O-H stretch as a broad band around 3400 cm^{-1} .

In the ammine complexes besides the N-H stretch at $3300\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$, a medium sharp band appears

at 1550 cm^{-1} which may probably be due to degenerate deformation of NH_3 . A similar type of band occurring at 870 cm^{-1} may be for NH_3 rocking vibration, but the band due to symmetric NH_3 deformation nearing 1300 cm^{-1} could not be definitely ascertained in the midst of other bands.

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